

Effect of Organizational Communication and Transformational Leadership on Increasing Employee Work Motivation at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency During the Covid 19 Pandemic

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Abstract:- The existence of educators (teachers) and education staff are human resources for SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency and are the most important assets owned by the institution and taken into account by school managers. The reliability and capacity of human resources, teachers and educational staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency have a duty to continue to be able to improve quality and affordable competencies for students in order to realize the highest degree of education. This study aims to determine the effect of organizational communication and transformational leadership of the principal on increasing the work motivation of teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency. The research approach used is quantitative. All teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency, totaling 67 people, were sampled in this study. The analytical technique used in this research is multiple linear regression analysis. The results of data analysis show that: 1. Organizational communication has a significant influence on the work motivation of teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency by 0.301 or 30.1%; 2. Transformational leadership has a significant influence on the work motivation of teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency by 0.354 or 35.4%; 3. Organizational communication and transformational leadership have a significant effect simultaneously on the work motivation of teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency by 0.245 or 24.5%.

Keywords:- Organizational Communication, Transformational Leadership, Work Motivation.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Handoko (2011), communication is the process of effectively delivering messages and information in the form of ideas, facts, thoughts, and emotions that are easily understood by two or more people. Communication is basically a basic human need that affects the behavior of all humans in an organization. Communication within an organization can be used as a driving force for organizational processes.

According to Robbins quoted by Hardjana (1998), communication carries out four main functions in a group or organization, namely: control (control, supervision), motivation, disclosure (emotional), and information. Communication acts to control member behavior in several ways. Every organization has a hierarchy of authority and formal guidelines that employees must follow. Organizational communication between executives and their subordinates is vertical. Vertically, the existing communication is about giving relevant instructions to employees and socializing decision making. Communication between superiors and subordinates, or between subordinates, often fosters a spirit of individual cooperation. Effective communication is the glue for organizational members.

Motivating leaders create conditions that inspire employees to work hard. Highly motivated employees are essential to achieve consistent high performance results. Executives adopt a leadership approach that reflects the perception that employee productivity is an important and irreplaceable part of achieving company goals.

Transformational Leadership is the effort of a leader in changing from a vision and mission into action and is carried out by making a clear vision, motivating staff to be creative, innovative, building a learning culture, and building effective communication. A true transformational leader gives their members more room to hone the skills they need in the workplace. This flexibility allows them to be more creative, innovate, find new solutions to old problems, and look to the future.

According to Dedy, et al (2019: 232) in general the definition or understanding of motivation can be interpreted as a goal or impetus, with the actual goal being the main driving force for a person in trying to get or achieve what he wants either positively or negatively.

The reliability and capacity of human resources, teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency have the duty to continue to be able to improve quality and affordable competencies for students in order to realize the highest degree of education. SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency aims especially in the field of life skills and entrepreneurship by trying to motivate students by increasing life skills to

provide graduates who do not continue to college. Educators (teachers) and education staff are human resources for SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency and are the most important assets owned by the institution and taken into account by school managers. The more important people are, actually boils down to the fact that people are the main thing in the organization. Humans set goals, innovate and achieve organizational goals. Human resources stimulate creativity in every organization. Without effective human resources, the organization will not be able to achieve its goals. Human resources make other organizational resources work. The availability of the number of teachers and staff is one of the great potentials of SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency. Continuous improvement of organizational performance requires effective Human Resources (HR). Teachers and Education Staff who have a dedicated attitude, discipline and professional competence are most likely to achieve effective work results in learning.

Thus, in this study the theme related to the work motivation of teachers and education staff will be raised. Organizational communication and leadership at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency are factors that are thought to have a significant influence on the work motivation of teachers and education staff.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in writing this thesis is the Quantitative Method. Methods of collecting data in this study using a questionnaire. The population in this study were all teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency, amounting to 67 people. The data analysis technique used in this research is descriptive statistical analysis with multiple regression analysis method. The form of the questionnaire used is a questionnaire with a Likert scale. Variable statements X_1 (Organizational Communication) and X_2 (Transformational Leadership) are declared valid with R count more than R table (0.2404). The variable statement instrument used as the questionnaire was declared reliable with a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.942 on the statement item variable X_1 , 0.883 on the statement item variable X_2 , and 0.724 on the statement item variable Y.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the sample obtained by respondents as many as 67 people with an age range of 27 - 54 years, 34 of whom

are male, and 33 of them are female. Respondents as many as 22 people have employment status as Civil Servants (PNS) and 45 people have employment status as Non Civil Servants (Non PNS). Respondents as many as 49 people work as teachers, 8 people work as education staff and 8 other people work as other employees. In addition, 1 respondent has the latest education in junior high school, 9 people have the latest education in high school/equivalent, 40 people have the latest education at Strata 1/Bachelor, and 17 others have the latest education at Strata 2/Master.

Variable statements X_1 (Organizational Communication) and X_2 (Transformational Leadership) are declared valid with R count more than R table (0.2404). The variable statement instrument used as the questionnaire was declared reliable with Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.942 on the statement item variable X_1 , 0.883 on the statement item variable X_2 , and 0.724 on the statement item variable Y.

Based on the results of multiple regression analysis, the constant value was 23.105. This means, if the variable conditions (X_1) and (X_2) are considered constant, then the Y variable is 23.105. The regression coefficient values in X_1 and X_2 are positive so it can be said that these variables have a positive relationship to the variable (Y). This means that if X_1 and X_2 have an increase in one-unit variable, it will result in the Y variable also increasing by the value of the regression coefficient.

$$Y = 23.105 + 0.301 X_1 + 0.354 X_2 + e$$

In addition, with a coefficient of determination of 0.245 or 24.5%. This means that the independent variables organizational communication (X_1) and transformational leadership (X_2) can explain the dependent variable work motivation (Y) by 24.5%, while the remaining 75.5% is explained by other factors not examined.

➤ *Multiple Linear Regression Analysis*

In this study there are three variables, of which two are independent variables, namely Organizational Communication (X_1), Transformational Leadership (X_2) and the dependent variable, namely work motivation (Y). This multiple linear regression analysis aims to solve the relationship problem of the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table 4.46 Multiple linear regression model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	23,105	6,463		3,575	,001
Organizational Communication	,301	,113	,320	2,666	,010
Transformational Leadership	,354	,148	,286	2,385	,020

➤ *Simultaneous Test (F Test)*

The results of the F test in this study can be seen in table 4.52 below:

Table 4.52 Simultaneous test results (F test)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	541,891	2	270,946	11,724	,000 ^b
Residual	1479,094	64	23,111		
Total	2020,985	66			

a. Dependent Variable: Motivasi_Kerja

b. Predictors: (Constant), Transformational Leadership, Organizational Communication

Based on table 4.52 of the results of the F test in this study, the calculated F value was 11.724 with a significance number (P value) of 0.000. With a significance level of 95% ($\alpha = 0.05$). The significance value (P value) is $0.000 < 0.05$. On the basis of this comparison, then H_0 is rejected or means that organizational communication variables (X1), and transformational leadership (X2) have a significant influence simultaneously on the work motivation variable (Y).

The Transformational Leadership of the Principal of SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency is classified as good, reinforced by the results of a survey of 67 respondents, 39 of whom agree that the principal's transformational leadership has a role for teachers and educational staff in achieving common goals. In addition, it was strengthened by 34 respondents who agreed that the transformational leadership of the Principal at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency had paid attention to the structure in the process of achieving organizational goals, further strengthened by 41 respondents who claimed that the leadership (Principal) of SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency prioritized mutual respect for employees (Teachers and Educational Staff).

➤ *The Effect of Organizational Communication on the Work Motivation of Teachers and Educational Staff*

This study shows that the organizational communication variable (X1) has a positive influence on the work motivation variable (Y) for teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency. This means that the better the Organizational Communication that occurs in the school environment, the more work motivation of teachers and education staff will increase.

Good organizational communication will facilitate and accelerate the increase in behavior change in the form of work motivation, while bad organizational communication will slow down and hinder the increase in work motivation. From the description above, it implies that transformational leadership and organizational communication play a very important role in increasing the work motivation of teachers and educational staff, especially in improving performance and in achievement outside the school environment. Transformational leadership and good organizational communication will have an indirect impact on school achievement.

Through the results above, it is clear that organizational communication has an influence on work motivation. This is also related to and in accordance with the statement of Robbins Robbins and Judge (2015:223) regarding the four main functions carried out by communication within the organization, namely: for control, motivation, emotional expression, and information.

➤ *The Effect of Transformational Leadership on the Work Motivation of Teachers and Educational Staff*

In this study, it shows that the Transformational Leadership variable (X2) has a positive influence on the work motivation variable (Y) for teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency. This means that the better the Transformational Leadership is carried out by the principal, the more work motivation of teachers and educational staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency, but the less good the Principal's Transformational Leadership, the lower the work motivation of teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Regency. Tangerang.

Transformational leadership is described as a leadership style that can stimulate or motivate employees to grow and achieve results. In addition, the principal must also be able to create a friendly school climate, advise students, encourage all staff, and so on. The principal's transformational leadership is able to exert influence which is shown through strong self-confidence so that he becomes an example for all components of the organization he leads, invites teachers and educational staff to view threats as opportunities to learn through the motivation provided so that teachers and educational staff are encouraged to be innovative and creative. , as well as paying attention to teachers and educational staff by taking into account the characteristics of each teacher and educational staff.

➤ *The Influence of Organizational Communication and Transformational Leadership on the Work Motivation of Teachers and Educational Staff*

A leader who uses a transformational leadership style invites all employees to work even harder by providing good examples, delegation of authority according to their duties and functions as well as good communication with all his staff so that the implementation of tasks and functions will go well so that all employees will feel comfortable. comfortable at work so that it can improve performance and employees feel satisfaction at work.

This research shows that organizational communication (X_1) and transformational leadership (X_2) variables have a significant effect simultaneously on the work motivation variable (Y). Based on the results of the F test in this study, the calculated F value was 11.724 with a significance number (P value) of 0.000. With a significance level of 95% ($\alpha = 0.05$). The significance value (P value) is $0.000 < 0.05$. On the basis of this comparison, then H_0 is rejected or means that organizational communication variables (X_1), and transformational leadership (X_2) have a significant influence simultaneously on the work motivation variable (Y).

From the description above, it indicates that organizational communication and transformational leadership have a very important role in increasing the work motivation of teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency. With good organizational communication and transformational leadership, it will also have an indirect impact on school achievement.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the description and discussion of research results, it can be concluded that Organizational Communication has a significant influence on the work motivation of teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency. Transformational leadership has a positive influence on the work motivation of teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency. This means that the better the Transformational Leadership is carried out by the principal, the more work motivation of teachers and educational staff at SMAN 2 Tangerang Regency, but the less good the Principal's Transformational Leadership, the lower the work motivation of teachers and education staff at SMAN 2 Regency. Tangerang. This research shows that organizational communication and transformational leadership have a significant effect simultaneously on work motivation.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Andre Hardjana. 2019. Komunikasi Organisasi: Strategi Interaksi dan Kepemimpinan. Jakarta: PT. Rajagrafindo Persada.
- [2]. Arni Muhammad. 2005. Komunikasi Organisasi. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara.
- [3]. Pace, R. Wayne., Don F. Faules. (2018). Komunikasi Organisasi: Strategi Meningkatkan Kinerja Perusahaan. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [4]. Choiriyah, Endah A, Endi S. 2020. Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan Komunikasi Organisasi: Perannya terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. Management and Business Review: [Vol.4, No.2, Desember 2020. Hal. 127-135]. [ISSN: 2541-5808, Online]
- [5]. Dhea WS, Yuliani RP. 2019. Pengaruh Komunikasi Organisasi Terhadap Motivasi Kerja Karyawan Lembaga Pengelola Dana Pendidikan: *E-Proceeding of Management*. Vol.6, April 2019. Hal 1658-1664]. [ISSN: 2355-9357].
- [6]. Diana A, Shahnaz Y. 2020. Pengaruh Komunikasi Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Gapa Citra Mandiri, Radio Dalam – Jakarta Selatan. Jurnal Disrupsi Bisnis: [Vol. 3, No.1, Januari 2020. Hal. 28 – 43]. [ISSN 2621-797X].
- [7]. Hilman Hilmawan, Yumhi. 2019. Pengaruh Komunikasi dan Kepemimpinan Transformasional Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Pegawai Rutan Klas IIB Rangkasbitung. *The Asia Pacific Journal of Management: Journal of Management Studies*. [Vol.6, No.1, 2019]. [ISSN: 2407-6325].
- [8]. I Made GAD, Ni Ketut S. 2018. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Disiplin Kerja dan Komunikasi Terhadap Motivasi Kerja Pada The Jayakarta Bali. E-Jurnal Manajemen Unud: Vol.7, No.6, 2018. Hal.2913-2941]. [ISSN: 2302-8912]. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24843/EJMUNUD.2018.v7.i06.p3>]
- [9]. Meylinda T, Made Subudi. 2018. Pengaruh Komunikasi Organisasi, Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan Keadilan Organisasi Terhadap *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* Serta Dampaknya Pada Kinerja dan Komitmen Organisasional. E-Journal Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Udayana: Vol.7, No.3, 2018. Hal. 837-868]. [ISSN: 2337-3067].
- [10]. Septi A, Nila K, Muhammad K. 2018. *The Influence Of The Transformational Leadership And Work Motivation On Teachers Performance*. International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research: [Vol. 7, Issue 7, ISSN: 2277 – 8616, Hal. 19-29].
- [11]. Suryati Eko P. 2019. Pengaruh Komunikasi, Motivasi Kerja dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Badan Kepegawaian Daerah Kabupaten Sidoarjo: Jurnal Ecopreneur 12. Vol.2, No. 2, ISSN: 2615-6237, 2019. Hal. 7-11. Universitas Teknologi Surabaya.
- [12]. Yulianti, H.M.Chiar, M. Syukri. 2021. Pengaruh Komunikasi Transformasional dan Komunikasi Kepala Sekolah Terhadap Motivasi Berprestasi Guru Sekolah Dasar Negeri Semparuk. Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran. Hal 1-11. Universitas Tanjungpura Pontianak.
- [13]. Ainun. 2020. *Pengertian Kepemimpinan: Tujuan, Teori, Fungsi, dan Contoh Leadership*. [Online]. Tersedia di: <https://salamadian.com/pengertian-kepemimpinan/>. [Diakses pada 04 Desember 2021].
- [14]. Akhmad S. 2014. *Mengenal Teori ERG yang Berkaitan Teori Maslow*. [Online]. Tersedia di: <https://visiuniversal.blogspot.com/2014/04/mengenal-teori-erg-yang-berkaitan-teori.html>. [Diakses pada 04 Desember 2021].
- [15]. Hootsuite. 2021. *Precentage of Global Digital Using social media on 2021*. [Online]. Tersedia: <https://andi.link/hootsuite-we-are-social-indonesian-digital-report-2021/>. [Diakses pada 20 Januari 2021].
- [16]. Imas, dkk (2015). *Makalah Teori Peniti Penyambung (The Linking Pin Model) Rensis Likert*. [Online]. Tersedia di : http://www.Academia.edu/22463218/Teori_Peniti_Penyambung. [Diakses pada 03 Desember 2021].

- [17]. Ramelanlifi. 2015. *Teori Motivasi Clayton Paul Alderfer (ERG)*. [Online]. Tersedia di: <http://ramelanlifi.blogspot.com/2015/05/clayton-paul-alderfer-seorang-pakar.html>. [Diakses pada 04 Desember 2021].
- [18]. Shalahuddin. 2021. *Karakteristik Kepemimpinan Transformasional*. [Online]. Tersedia di: <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/publications/56599-ID-karakteristik-kepemimpinan-transformasio.pdf>. [Diakses pada 27 Januari 2022]